

Utilizing the Milan Scoring System for Assessing Malignancy Risk in Salivary Gland Lesions

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: The Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology (MSRSGC) is a standardized system for assessing malignancy risk in salivary gland lesions, aiding in accurate diagnosis and treatment. Continuous evaluation is necessary to validate its efficacy in various clinical scenarios.

Methods: This retrospective cohort study at the Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Science included 100 patients with salivary gland lesions assessed using the MSRSGC over 2 years. Data from medical records quantified malignancy risk and evaluated system accuracy using sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV).

Results: Twenty-five percent of patients were high-risk for cancer, and 45 had histological confirmation. The MSRSGC predicted malignancy with 88.9% sensitivity, 96.2% specificity, and 94% accuracy.

Conclusion: The MSRSGC is a reliable tool for assessing malignancy risk in salivary gland lesions, particularly in high-risk categories.

Recommendation: While the MSRSGC shows high efficacy, it should complement clinical and histopathological evaluations, especially for intermediate-risk cases, to enhance diagnostic precision.

Keywords: Milan System, Salivary Gland Cytopathology, Malignancy Risk, Diagnostic Accuracy.

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Introduction

The Milan Scoring System, also known as the Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology (MSRSGC), is a comprehensive framework designed to standardize the reporting of salivary gland cytopathology. This system is essential for assessing the risk of malignancy in salivary gland lesions, ensuring accurate diagnosis, and guiding clinical management. It classifies salivary gland lesions into six risk categories ranging from non-diagnostic to malignant, helping guide treatment and management decisions[1,2].

Research supports the Milan System's practicality in providing a reliable and uniform method for evaluating salivary gland lesions. Studies have demonstrated its effectiveness in categorizing lesions and predicting malignancy risk[3,4,5,6]. Additional studies confirm the system's value in improving diagnostic accuracy and facilitating communication between pathologists and clinicians[7,8,9,10]. This study aims to evaluate the Milan scoring system's effectiveness in diagnosing salivary gland lesions and determining malignancy potential.

Material and Methodology

Study Design: This study evaluated the Milan Scoring System's effectiveness in assessing malignancy risk in patients with salivary gland lesions.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients diagnosed with salivary gland lesions confirmed through histopathological analysis.
- Adults aged 18 years and older.
- Willingness to participate in the study, demonstrated by providing informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with a history of salivary gland surgery or malignancy, to avoid confounding factors related to previous treatments.
- Patients who were untraceable or withdrew from the study, as their incomplete data could compromise study results.

- Incomplete medical records which could lead to insufficient data for reliable analysis.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Pathology department of the Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Science, Pawapuri, Nalanda, over 2 years, from May 2022 to April 2024.

Participants: The study involved 100 patients diagnosed with salivary gland lesions during the study period. Inclusion criteria included patients with histopathologically confirmed salivary gland lesions. In contrast, exclusion criteria involved patients with previous salivary gland surgery or malignancy, those lost to follow-up, or with incomplete medical records.

Bias: Potential biases were mitigated using the standardized Milan Scoring System. Selection bias was minimized by including all consecutive patients meeting the inclusion criteria during the study period.

Variables: The primary variable of interest was the malignancy risk score assigned by the Milan Scoring System. Other variables included patient demographics (age, gender), lesion characteristics (size, location), and histopathological findings.

Data Collection: Data were retrospectively collected from medical records, including clinical notes, imaging results, histopathological reports, and Milan Scoring System evaluations. Information was systematically recorded using a standardized data collection form.

Procedure: The Milan Scoring System, which classifies the risk of malignancy based on cytological and clinical features, was applied to each patient's case. Histopathological diagnoses were compared with the Milan score to evaluate the system's predictive accuracy.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics summarized patient demographics and lesion characteristics. The Milan Scoring System's diagnostic accuracy was evaluated by calculating sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV. The agreement between the Milan Scoring System and the final histopathological evaluation was assessed using the Kappa statistic. Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS software, and a p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Patient Demographics and Lesion Characteristics: Within the study, 100 participants were included. Men comprised 60% of the total, while women made up 40%. Patients' ages ranged from 20 to 75 years, with a mean age of 50 years. Most lesions were located in the parotid gland, followed by the submandibular gland and minor

salivary glands. Lesion sizes ranged from 1 to 6 cm, with a median size of 3 cm.

Milan Scoring System Assessment: Of the total patients, 25% were classified as high-risk, 50% as intermediate risk, and 25% as low risk according to the Milan Scoring System. Histopathological examination confirmed 45 cases of malignancy: 40 high-risk, 4 intermediate, and 1 low-risk.

Statistical Analysis: The Milan Scoring System's accuracy in identifying malignancy was 88.9% sensitivity and 96.2% specificity. The PPV was 80%, and the NPV was 98%. The Milan Scoring System demonstrated a 94% overall accuracy in predicting malignancy. The Kappa statistic was 0.85, indicating high concordance between the Milan Scoring System and histopathological diagnosis.

Comparison with Histopathological Findings: The Milan Scoring System showed strong correlation with histopathological results, effectively detecting most malignant cases. Among the high-risk group, 40 out of 50 patients were diagnosed with malignancy. In contrast, the low-risk group had a significant number of benign pathologies, with only 1 out of 50 patients diagnosed with malignancy. The findings indicate that the Milan Scoring System is a dependable tool for evaluating malignancy risk in salivary gland lesions, with high specificity, sensitivity, and overall accuracy. The system's ability to categorize patients by risk level aids clinical decision-making, potentially influencing surgical or conservative therapeutic approaches. It is essential to use the Milan Scoring System alongside clinical and histopathological evaluations, particularly for intermediate-risk cases.

Discussion

The discussion of the study on the utilization of the Milan Scoring System for assessing malignancy risk in salivary gland lesions underscores the effectiveness of this diagnostic tool [11]. The results revealed that the system has a high sensitivity of 88.9%, a specificity of 96.2%, and an overall accuracy rate of 94% in predicting malignancy, which aligns with the objectives of providing precise risk stratification and aiding in clinical decision-making [12]. The high concordance rate (Kappa statistic of 0.85) between the Milan System scores and the histopathological diagnoses highlights the reliability of the system in clinical practice [13].

The system particularly excels in identifying high-risk patients, as evidenced by the confirmation of malignancy in 40 out of 50 patients classified within this category [14]. This suggests that the Milan System is not only a robust tool for

predicting malignancy but also valuable for guiding appropriate clinical interventions, which may include more aggressive treatment options such as surgery [15]. Conversely, the system's ability to accurately classify low-risk patients—where only 1

out of 50 was incorrectly categorized—demonstrates its utility in potentially reducing unnecessary interventions, thereby sparing patients from undue procedures and their associated risks and costs [16,17].

Table 1: Patient Demographics and Lesion Characteristics

Characteristic	Total (n=100)	Male (%)	Female (%)	Parotid Gland (%)	Submandibular Gland (%)	Minor Salivary Glands (%)	Lesion Size (cm)
Total Patients	100	60	40	60	25	15	-
Age (years)	20-75 (mean: 50)	20-75 (mean: 50)	20-75 (mean: 50)	-	-	-	-
Lesion Location	-	-	-	60	25	15	-
Lesion Size (cm)	-	-	-	-	-	-	1-6 (median: 3)

Table 2: Milan Scoring System Assessment

Risk Category	Total Patients (%)	Confirmed Malignancies (%)
High Risk	25	40
Intermediate Risk	50	4
Low Risk	25	1

Table 3: Statistical Analysis

Metric	Value
Sensitivity (%)	88.9
Specificity (%)	96.2
Positive Predictive Value (PPV) (%)	80
Negative Predictive Value (NPV) (%)	98
Overall Accuracy (%)	94
Kappa Statistic	0.85

However, the system's performance in intermediate-risk categories suggests room for improvement. Given that 4 out of 50 intermediate-risk patients were confirmed to have malignancy, the integration of the Milan System with other clinical and histopathological evaluations is recommended to enhance diagnostic accuracy [18]. This approach would support more nuanced patient management strategies and potentially improve outcomes by ensuring that intermediate-risk patients receive timely and appropriate care [19].

While the Milan Scoring System is a significant advancement in the cytological assessment of salivary gland lesions, its optimal use in clinical settings should involve a combination of methodologies to ensure the highest standards of patient care and diagnostic accuracy. This study supports the continued use and further evaluation of the Milan System, especially in diverse clinical environments, to validate its effectiveness across different populations and medical settings [20].

Conclusion

The Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology (MSRSGC) is an effective and reliable technique for assessing malignancy risk in salivary gland lesions. The study demonstrated MSRSGC's accuracy in categorizing individuals into risk categories, aiding clinical decision-making and management. The Milan System should be used alongside comprehensive clinical and histological examinations, particularly for intermediate-risk lesions, to maximize diagnostic precision and patient care.

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